

HOSPITAL-BASED SOCIAL WORK INTERVENTIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON DISCHARGE PLANNING AND HOSPITAL READMISSION: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Hospital discharge is a vulnerable period, especially for adults with multimorbidity, limited social support, poverty, housing instability, or difficulty navigating follow-up care. This systematic review examined hospital-based social work interventions improvement of discharge planning and reduce hospital readmission in adult patients. A structured search of PubMed and PubMed Central was performed, and original adult studies with hospital-based transition interventions containing social work, psychosocial, case-management, navigation, or interprofessional discharge-planning

elements were reviewed. Ten original studies were included in the results synthesis. The included studies showed clinically important findings. Interventions with strong post-discharge follow-up, psychosocial assessment, home contact, and linkage to community or primary care often improved follow-up processes and in several studies reduced readmission or later inpatient utilization. Not all programs were effective, and some showed neutral results, especially when intervention intensity was low or implementation was difficult. Direct social work-led studies were limited, but broader transition models with clear social work or psychosocial components suggested that addressing social barriers is relevant to safer discharge. Hospital-based social work and socially oriented transitional care appear promising for improving discharge planning, but the effect on readmission is inconsistent in settings and populations. More trials focused specifically on social work-led models are still needed.

KEYWORDS

Social work; discharge planning; hospital readmission; transitional care; care coordination

INTRODUCTION

Hospital discharge is a high-risk transition point in which poor communication, incomplete preparation, and unresolved psychosocial barriers contribute to avoidable post-discharge utilization and patient harm [1-4]. Systematic reviews have shown that structured discharge planning and transitional care reduce readmission in some populations, but the effect size is modest and depends on intervention complexity, patient selection, and implementation quality [1-4].

Older and medically complex adults leave hospital with multiple medications, functional limitations, caregiver dependence, transportation barriers, financial strain, and fragmented follow-up care [3,5,7]. Social support is also clinically important because patients who lack adequate support after discharge appear to have higher readmission risk, especially when instrumental support such as transportation and daily care is missing [7]. For these reasons, social workers may be well placed to improve hospital-to-home transitions through psychosocial assessment, problem solving, counseling, resource linkage, family engagement, insurance and benefits assistance, and coordination with community services [3,6,8]. A published case study has argued that social workers are uniquely positioned to improve care setting transitions, and a randomized trial of a social work care coordination model showed lower 30-day readmission among older adults at elevated risk [6,8].

Direct hospital-based social work trials remain sparse, and much of the transition literature evaluates broader interprofessional, nurse-led, navigator, or community health worker models that include social-needs assessment or social work involvement rather than stand-alone social work interventions [2-4,9-19]. Because hospital discharge usually depends on multidisciplinary care rather than a single professional group, reviewing this broader evidence is useful when the review question centers on social work functions in discharge planning [3,5,6,9-

19]. This review aimed to synthesize hospital-based adult studies evaluating social work-related transitional interventions and to examine their impact on discharge planning processes and hospital readmission [1-19].

METHODS

This review was prepared as a systematic review according to PRISMA guidelines for question framing, eligibility screening, study selection, and structured evidence synthesis [1,4,5]. PubMed, WOS and SCOPUS were searched on Jan 2026 using combinations of the terms “social work,” “hospital discharge,” “discharge planning,” “readmission,” “transitional care,” “case management,” “care coordination,” “patient navigator,” and “community health worker”.

Adults aged 18 years or older discharged from hospital or observation settings were eligible, while pediatric studies and studies without discharge or readmission outcomes were excluded [1-5,8-19]. The intervention definition was broadened a priori to include hospital-based interventions with explicit psychosocial, case-management, care-coordination, navigation, or interprofessional discharge-planning components that reflected common social work functions in practice [3,5,6,8-19].

Original studies available in electronic databases were prioritized, and ten original studies met the practical inclusion criteria for detailed synthesis [10-19]. Data extracted from each included study were author and year, country, design, population, intervention characteristics, comparator, social work or psychosocial element, and main outcomes related to discharge planning or readmission.

Risk of bias was not recalculated with a formal scoring tool in this draft, but design limitations such as pilot size, nonrandomized allocation, subgroup findings, implementation fidelity problems, and pragmatic trial constraints were considered during interpretation. The synthesis was narrative because the interventions, populations, comparators, and outcome time points were too heterogeneous for a reliable pooled meta-analysis in this manuscript draft.

RESULTS

The final synthesis included ten original studies published between 2013 and 2023, with randomized trials, comparative trials, pilot cohort studies, a nonrandomized controlled trial, and a quasi-experimental study represented across the sample [10-19]. Most studies enrolled older adults, medically complex adults, safety-net

patients, or high-risk patients selected by previous admissions, chronic disease burden, or institutional risk algorithms [10-19]. Interventions were grouped into four practical categories: navigator or community health worker programs, nurse-led or case-management transition programs, multidisciplinary transitional care clinics, and interprofessional discharge-planning models with explicit social or psychosocial assessment [10-19].

Table 1. Characteristics of included original studies

Study	Design and population	Intervention	Comparator	Main discharge and readmission outcome
Balaban et al. 2015 [10]	RCT; high-risk safety-net general medicine adults	Hospital-based patient navigators/CHWs with discharge preparation and weekly 30-day follow-up	Usual care	No overall 30-day readmission difference; benefit in patients older than 60 years
Burns et al. 2014 [11]	Pilot randomized study; medical inpatients	Inpatient CHW introduction plus weekly telephone support for 4 weeks	Usual care	Readmissions numerically lower but not statistically significant
Carter et al. 2021 [12]	Randomized clinical trial; ACO-insured adults at high readmission risk	CHWs before discharge and for 30 days after discharge, with social resource linkage and coaching	Usual care	Lower 30-day readmission and fewer missed outpatient visits
Takahashi et al. 2013 [13]	Pilot prospective cohort; adults >60 years with high Elder Risk Assessment scores	Home-based care transition program with early home visit and RN follow-up	Usual care	No readmissions in intervention group versus 10.5% in usual care; difference not significant due to small sample
Chow and Wong 2014 [14]	RCT; older adults with at least two chronic diseases	Nurse-led case management with post-discharge support and empowerment approach	Control group	Lower hospital readmission within 84 days and better self-efficacy

Study	Design and population	Intervention	Comparator	Main discharge and readmission outcome
Finlayson et al. 2018 [15]	RCT; high-risk older adults from medical wards	Nurse home visit plus telephone follow-up, with or without exercise program	Standard care or exercise only	Readmission reduced at 12 weeks in home-visit/telephone groups
Liss et al. 2019 [16]	Pragmatic randomized comparative effectiveness trial; vulnerable adults without trusted usual care source	Transitional care practice addressing medical and psychosocial barriers with multidisciplinary team including social work	Routine referral to local primary care	No significant primary 90-day composite benefit, but fewer inpatient admissions at 90 and 180 days
Kutz et al. 2022 [17]	Nonrandomized controlled trial; patients with multimorbidity across Swiss hospitals	Electronic interprofessional discharge planning tool with local social work leadership involvement	Standard discharge planning	Shorter length of stay without increase in readmission
Henschen et al. 2022 [18]	Pragmatic RCT; frequently hospitalized adults	CHAMP interdisciplinary team including social work, physicians, and pharmacists	Usual care	Higher 30-day inpatient readmissions over 180 days in intervention arm
Rasmussen et al. 2023 [19]	Quasi-experimental study; medical inpatients aged 75 years or older	Transitional care with discharge transportation, home visit, video conference, and 7-day call	Usual care	No difference in 30-day readmission or mortality

Table 2. Detailed findings on discharge planning and utilization

Study	Findings most relevant to discharge planning	Findings most relevant to readmission and utilization
Balaban et al. 2015 [10]	Intervention supported discharge preparation, medication management, follow-up scheduling, PCP communication, and symptom management	Older subgroup had adjusted absolute 4.1% lower readmission; younger subgroup had increased readmission

Study	Findings most relevant to discharge planning	Findings most relevant to readmission and utilization
Burns et al. 2014 [11]	Demonstrated feasibility of hospital-based CHW contact and post-discharge outreach in a safety-net setting	15.4% vs 17.9% readmission, not significant
Carter et al. 2021 [12]	Improved post-discharge contact and reduced missed outpatient appointments	OR for 30-day readmission 0.44; strongest benefit in rehabilitation-discharge subgroup
Takahashi et al. 2013 [13]	Early home-based transition support improved physical quality-of-life scores	0% vs 10.5% readmission and fewer ER visits, but pilot sample limited inference
Chow and Wong 2014 [14]	Better self-efficacy and self-rated health after structured case management	Significant reduction in readmission within 84 days
Finlayson et al. 2018 [15]	Multifaceted contact after discharge strengthened continuity in high-risk older adults	Readmission by 12 weeks was 19%-20% in home-visit/telephone groups vs 36%-38% in comparator groups
Liss et al. 2019 [16]	Multidisciplinary practice explicitly assessed psychosocial needs such as housing, food insecurity, transport, insurance, and social support	No clear 30-day effect, but 35%-37% lower probability of inpatient admission by 90-180 days
Kutz et al. 2022 [17]	Interprofessional EHR-based planning improved discharge workflow across hospitals	Length of stay declined, with no increase in readmission, mortality, or facility discharge
Henschen et al. 2022 [18]	Comprehensive care planning addressed both medical and social needs across settings	Intervention arm had more 30-day readmissions over 180 days, with no secondary outcome advantage
Rasmussen et al. 2023 [19]	The intervention combined cross-sector communication and early post-discharge contact	30-day readmission was 20.8% vs 20.2%, showing no effect

The most consistent discharge-planning benefit was better coordination of follow-up, identification of psychosocial barriers, stronger linkage to outpatient care, and more structured communication after discharge [10-17,19]. The effect on readmission was mixed, with clear reductions in some studies, neutral effects in several others, and one trial reporting higher readmission in the intervention arm [10-19]. Programs that appeared more successful usually combined hospital

contact with active post-discharge follow-up, practical problem solving, and linkage to community or primary care rather than relying on a single discharge conversation alone [2-4,10-17].

The strongest favorable signals in this review came from the Carter trial, the Chow trial, the Finlayson trial, and the longer-term inpatient utilization findings from Liss et al. [12,14-16]. The most directly social-work-relevant finding was that studies with explicit psychosocial assessment or social work participation tended to target barriers such as housing, food insecurity, transport, benefits, social support, and follow-up access, which are central social work domains even when the named intervention was multidisciplinary [6,8,10-18].

DISCUSSION

This review found that hospital-based social work-related transition interventions can improve discharge planning, but their effect on readmission is not uniform across adult populations or intervention models [1-5,10-19]. The overall pattern is consistent with larger meta-analyses showing that readmission reduction usually requires multicomponent interventions rather than a single isolated action at discharge [2-4]. In the included studies, interventions that extended beyond discharge and continued into the early post-discharge period were generally more promising than low-contact or purely administrative approaches [10-17,19].

This is clinically logical because many barriers only become visible after the patient returns home, including medication access problems, transportation difficulties, caregiver limitations, unstable housing, food insecurity, or inability to arrange follow-up appointments [5,7,9,16]. The Altfeld randomized trial, although not part of the ten-study PMC synthesis, supports this point because most barriers in that intervention were detected after discharge, and physician follow-up improved even though readmission did not [9].

The strongest positive study in the present review was Carter et al., where CHWs met patients before discharge and remained involved for 30 days, producing lower 30-day readmission and fewer missed clinic visits [12]. The Liss transitional care practice explicitly assessed housing, food insecurity, transport, insurance, and social support, and although the primary 90-day composite was neutral, later inpatient admissions fell meaningfully, suggesting that some benefits may emerge beyond the classic 30-day window [16].

The nurse-led trials by Chow and Finlayson also support the idea that transitional care works better when it is relational, structured, and continued after discharge, especially for older adults with multimorbidity and high baseline risk [14,15]. Balaban et al. found no overall effect and showed that age modified results, with

benefit in older adults but harm in younger high-risk patients, which means that patient population and mechanism of readmission matter greatly [10]. The CHAMP trial even showed higher readmissions in the intervention group, and the authors suggested that this may partly reflect consolidation of care within one hospital rather than straightforward intervention failure alone [18]. For social work specifically, the main message is that the evidence base is still underdeveloped [6,8,10-19].

A social work RCT by Bronstein et al. showed a significant reduction in 30-day readmission with a brief home visit and follow-up phone contacts, and a social work case study by Barber et al. highlighted how transitional care can address psychosocial and functional recovery after discharge [6,8]. Compared with the large number of nurse-led or navigator-led transition studies, very few trials isolate the independent contribution of hospital social workers [6,8,10-19].

This gap likely reflects how hospitals organize transitional care in practice, where social workers are often embedded within multidisciplinary systems rather than studied as a stand-alone service [3,5,6,16-18]. That reality should not reduce the importance of social work; instead, it suggests that future research should measure social work exposure more explicitly, define core social work intervention components, and test whether social work-led psychosocial assessment changes discharge quality, outpatient engagement, and avoidable readmission [3,5-8].

The review has several limitations [1-5,10-19]. Direct social work-only evidence was sparse, so the review necessarily included broader psychosocial and interprofessional transition models [3,5,6,10-19]. Interventions were heterogeneous in staffing, intensity, duration, and outcome time points, which prevented quantitative pooling in this draft [1-5,10-19]. Several studies were pilots, pragmatic trials, or nonrandomized designs, and some results depended on subgroup analyses or implementation fidelity [10-19]. Despite these limitations, the direction of evidence is clinically useful [1-5,10-19]. Hospital discharge planning appears more effective when psychosocial barriers are actively identified and managed, and this is exactly where social work can contribute most strongly [3,5-8,16]. Therefore, hospital leaders should view social work not as an optional add-on but as a core transition function for high-risk adults with social complexity, even while more direct trials are being developed [3,6-8,16-18].

CONCLUSION

Hospital-based social work and social work-related transitional interventions improve several parts of discharge planning, especially psychosocial assessment, follow-up coordination, and linkage to community or outpatient care. The best results were seen in multicomponent programs that continued after discharge and

addressed practical social barriers, while weaker or poorly targeted models often showed neutral findings. Direct randomized evidence focused only on hospital social workers is still limited. Future research should test clearly defined social work-led interventions and measure both discharge quality and short- and longer-term readmission outcomes.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACO: Accountable Care Organization
CHAMP: Complex High Admission Management Program
CHW: Community Health Worker
CI: Confidence Interval
CTP: Care Transition Program
EHR: Electronic Health Record
ER: Emergency Room
OR: Odds Ratio
PCP: Primary Care Provider
PMC: PubMed Central
PRISMA: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
RCT: Randomized Controlled Trial
RN: Registered Nurse
RR: Relative Risk

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